

SHREDINGER OPERATORI DISKRET SPEKTRINING XOS QIYMATLARI HAQIDA

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[1] ishda $d = 1, 2, \dots$ - o‘lchamli \mathbb{Z}^d $\mu > 0$ potentsiilli ikkita bir xil zarrachali (bozon) sistema panjarada juft-jufti bilan kontakt ta’sirlashuvchi gamiltonianiga mos ikki zarrachali diskret Shredinger operatori $h_\mu(k)$, $k \in \mathbb{T}^d$, $d = 1, 2$ qaralgan. Ushbu operator xos qiymati uchun muhim spektr tubidagi yoyilmalar olingan.

[2] ishda ixtiyoriy o‘lchamli panjarada qo‘shni tugunlarda ta’sirlashuvchi ikkita fermionli sistema gamiltonianiga mos $h_\mu(k)$, $k \in \mathbb{T}^d$ ikki zarrachali diskret Shredinger operatori qaralgan. $h_\mu(k)$ ning zarrachalar ta’sirlashuv energiyasi $\mu > 0$ va sistema kvaziimpul’si $k \in \mathbb{T}^1$ ga bog‘liq muhim spektrdan o‘ngda yoki yagona xos qiymatga ega yoki xos qiymatga ega emasligi isbotlangan.

Ushbu ishda ikki o‘lchamli panjarada qo‘shni tugunlarda ta’sirlashuvchi ikkita fermionli sistema gamiltonianiga mos $h_\mu(k)$, $k \in \mathbb{T}^2$ ikki zarrachali diskret Shredinger operatori qaraladi. $h_\mu(k)$ operatorning muhim spektrdan chapda xos qiymatga ega yoki xos qiymatga ega bo‘lmaydigan qiymatlari ajratib ko‘rsatiladi. Sistema kvaziimpulsining ba’zi qiymatlarining aniq ko‘rinishi topilgan.

Faraz qilaylik \mathbb{T}^2 - ikki o‘lchamli tor, ya’ni qarama-qarshi tomonlari ayniy $(-\pi, \pi]^2$ kvadrat bo‘lsin. Uni qo‘shish va songa ko‘paytirish amallari \mathbb{R}^2 da $(2\pi\mathbb{Z})^2$ modul bo‘yicha qo‘shish va songa ko‘paytirish amallari kabi kiritilgan abel guruhi deb qarash mumkin.

$L_2(\mathbb{T}^2)$ -orqali \mathbb{T}^2 da aniqlangan kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi funksiyalarning gilbert fazosini belgilaymiz.

$L_2^t(\mathbb{T}^2) = \{f \in L_2(\mathbb{T}^2) : f(-\mathbf{q}) = -f(\mathbf{q})\}$ – Hilbert fazosida quyidagicha aniqlangan $h_\mu(k)$, $k \in \mathbb{T}^2$, operatorni qaraymiz

$$h_\mu(k) = h_0(k) - \mu v.$$

Qo'zg'almas $h_0(k)$ operator $E_k(q)$ funksiyaga ko'paytirish operatoridir, ya'ni

$$(h_0(k)f)(\mathbf{q}) = E_k(\mathbf{q})f(\mathbf{q}), \quad f \in L_2^t(\mathbb{T}^2),$$

bunda

$$E_k(\mathbf{q}) = \varepsilon\left(\frac{k}{2} + \mathbf{q}\right) + \varepsilon\left(\frac{k}{2} - \mathbf{q}\right),$$

$$\varepsilon(\mathbf{q}) = \sum_{i=1}^2 (1 - \cos q^{(i)}).$$

Ta'sir operatori (qo'zg'alish operatori) $v - L_2^t(\mathbb{T}^2)$ Hilbert fazosida quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$(vf)(\mathbf{q}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \sum_{i=1}^2 \sin q^{(i)} \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \sin t^{(i)} f(\mathbf{t}) dt.$$

Ravshanki, v - integral operator bo'lib, rangi 2 - dan oshmaydi. Muhim spektr turg'unligi haqidagi Veyl teoremasiga ko'ra ([4] ga q.) $h_\mu(k)$ operatorning muhim spektri $\sigma_{ess}(h_\mu(k))$ berilgan $\mu \geq 0$ parametrdan bog'liq emas va h_0 operatorning spektri bilan ustma-ust tushadi. Shunday qilib

$$\sigma_{ess}(h_\mu(k)) = [\varepsilon_{min}(k), \varepsilon_{max}(k)]$$

tenglik o'rinli, bunda

$$\varepsilon_{min}(k) = \min_{\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{T}^2} E_k(\mathbf{q}) = 2 \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(1 - \cos \frac{k^{(j)}}{2}\right) \geq 0,$$

$$\varepsilon_{max}(k) = \max_{q \in \mathbb{T}^2} E_k(q) = 2 \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(1 + \cos \frac{k^{(j)}}{2} \right) \leq 8$$

Π – orqali $(-\pi, \pi]^2$ kubning chegarasini belgilaymiz. Aniqlanishiga ko‘ra

$$\Pi = \{k = (k^{(1)}, k^{(2)}) \in \mathbb{T}^2: \text{birorta } j = 1, 2 \text{ uchun } k^{(j)} = \pi\}$$

Har bir $k \in \mathbb{T}^2 \setminus \Pi$ uchun quyidagicha belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$v^{(i)}(k) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int_{\mathbb{T}^2} \frac{\sin^2 q^{(i)} dq}{E_k(q) - \varepsilon_{min}(k)}$$

va

$$\mu^{(i)}(k) = \frac{1}{v^{(i)}(k)} > 0.$$

Aytish joizki, har bir $k \in \mathbb{T}^2 \setminus \Pi$ uchun

$$E_k(q) = 2 \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(1 - \cos \frac{k^{(j)}}{2} \cos q^{(j)} \right)$$

funksiya $q = (0, 0)$ nuqtada aynimagan minimumga ega bo‘lganligi uchun yuqoridagi integral chekli.

Π_{k_1} – orqali quyidagi to‘plamni belgilaylik:

$$\Pi_{k_1} = \{k \in \mathbb{T}^2: k_2 = \pi\}$$

Teorema. $k_1 = (k, \pi)$ bo'lsin, ya'ni $k \in \Pi_{k_1}$. U holda $0 < \mu < 2 \cos \frac{k_1}{2}$ bo'lsa,

$h_\mu(k_1)$ operator muhim spektrdan chapda yagona xos qiymatga ega va $\mu > 2 \cos \frac{k_1}{2}$ bo'lsa, muhim spektrdan chapda ikkita xos qiymati mavjud hamda ushbu xos qiymatlar quyidagi ko'rinishga ega:

$$z = 4 - \sqrt{4 \cos^2 \frac{k^{(2)}}{2} + \frac{\mu^2}{4}},$$

$$z = 4 - \left(\frac{2 \cos \frac{k_1}{2}}{\mu} + \frac{\mu}{2} \right).$$

Endi ishimizni ikkinchi qismiga o'tamiz.

Har bir $k \in \mathbb{T}^2 \setminus \Pi$ uchun quyidagi to'plamni kiritamiz:

$$M_{>}(k) = \{\mu \in \mathbb{R}_+ : \mu > \mu_i(k), i = 1, 2\}$$

Teorema. $\mu \in M_{>}(k), i = 1, 2, k \in \mathbb{T}^2$ bo'lsin. U holda $h_\mu(k)$ operator muhim spektrdan chapda ikkita xos qiymatga ega.

Eslatma. $k_1 = (\pi; 0)$ bo'lsin, ya'ni $k_1 \in \Pi$. U holda $\mu_{(1)}(k_1) = 0$ va $\mu_{(2)}(k_1) = 2$ tenglik o'rinli.

Teorema. $k = k_1$ bo'lsin. U holda agar $0 < \mu < 2$ bo'lsa, $h_\mu(k_1)$ operator muhim spektrdan chapda yagona xos qiymatga ega va $\mu > 2$ bo'lsa ikkita xos qiymati mavjud hamda ushbu xos qiymatlar quyidagi ko'rinishga ega:

$$z^{(1)}(\mu, k_1) = 4 - \sqrt{4 + \frac{1}{4}\mu^2},$$

$$z^{(2)}(\mu, k_1) = 4 - \left(\frac{\mu}{2} + \frac{2}{\mu} \right).$$

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